

Behaviour of Disodium Salt of *p*-Nitrobenzeneazochromotropic Acid (Chromotrope 2B) as a Colloidal Electrolyte

Suresh C. Srivastava*, Roshan Lal Sethi, and Arun K. Dey

p-Nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (sodium salt, trivial name: Chromotrope 2B) has been used as a metallochromic indicator in complexometric titrations. Deviations from true stoichiometry in the composition of the metal chelates were observed when the solutions of Chromotrope 2B used were not very dilute. Nevertheless, when the solutions of the reagent employed were fairly dilute, an exact composition of the metal chelates was revealed. Chromotrope 2B appears to behave as a colloidal electrolyte, as has been noted in the case of other dyes used as chelating agents¹.

The nature of solutions of *p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid has been studied by electrical conductance measurements with a Leeds & Northrup Kohlrausch slidewire with an audiofrequency oscillator in the circuit, operated by a 220 V/50 cycles a.c. mains, using a dip-type measuring cell having a cell constant of 0.580. Freshly prepared aqueous solutions of disodium salt of *p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid (B.D.H. indicator) were used.

FIG. 1. Conductance of disodium salt of *p*-nitrobenzeneazochromotropic acid at various temperatures.

The specific conductance of solutions of the reagent was determined at different dilutions at five different temperatures and the temperature of zero conductance, extrapolated from the curves in Fig. 1, was found to lie at -16.5° . The temperature coefficient

Present addresses: * Department of Nuclear Engineering, Brookhaven National Laboratory, Upton, L. I., New York, U.S.A.

† Central Electrochemical Research Institute, Karaikudi.

1. Sangal and Dey, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1963, 21B, 600.

per degree centigrade per hundred of the conductance at 35° provides values between 1.80 and 1.95.

From these, it may be suggested that an aqueous solution of disodium salt of this reagent is not exactly a true solution and has some colloidal characteristics. Hence consideration is necessary also for this aspect in the behaviour of the reagent and therefore it is imperative that very dilute solutions of the reagent be employed in physico-chemical measurements, where the solutions would behave as true solutions, as has been emphasised by Dey². If the solutions used are not very dilute, deviations in the composition from true stoichiometry are apt to occur.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD,
ALLAHABAD.

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